

COAGULATION OF COLLOIDS BY BIMETALLIC JUNCTIONS

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The effect of bimetallic couples such as Mg-Fe, Mg-Zn, Mg-Mn, Mg-Cu and Mg-Ag has been studied with respect to coagulation of colloidal solutions of Fe_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 , As_2S_3 and V_2O_5 . The rate of coagulation has been found to vary with the nature of the couple and the charge of the colloids and the function of evolved hydrogen bubble in the coagulation phenomenon discussed.

In a previous note from this laboratory (Ganguly, *Curr. Sci.*, 1941, 10, 75) it has been shown that bimetallic junctions (e.g. iron-aluminium couple) can coagulate colloidal solutions. It has also been pointed out that coagulation always proceeds from certain active points on the couple and it occurs most at the points where the active hydrogen is most vigorously evolved. In the present paper the effect of bimetallic couples has been studied in detail. An attempt has also been made to see whether atomic hydrogen plays any part during the coagulation process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Four colloidal solutions, two positively charged and two negatively charged, were selected for investigation. These were prepared as follows.

Ferric Oxide Sol.—A few drops of 30% solution of ferric chloride were added to 500 c.c. of briskly boiling distilled water. A deep brown, transparent, positively charged sol was obtained.

Aluminium oxide sol was prepared according to the method of Crum (*Annalen*, 1853, 89, 156) by prolonged heating of a little aluminium acetate with a large volume of water on the water-bath till no smell of acetic acid was perceptible. A slightly opalescent, positively charged sol was obtained. It was practically free from acid.

Arsenious sulphide sol was prepared by the method of Linder and Picton (*J. Chem Soc.*, 1892, 61, 137) as follows: arsenious oxide (0.5 g.) was boiled with 500 c.c. distilled water till solution was complete. When cooled, a current of H_2S was passed through the solution till no more deepening of colour took place. Excess of H_2S was removed by passing a rapid stream of hydrogen gas through the solution. The solution was filtered and kept in a stoppered flask.

Vanadium pentoxide sol was prepared by the method of Biltz. Ammonium vanadate (7g. approx.) was triturated in a mortar with hydrochloric acid. The red precipitate was filtered and washed continuously till the filtrate assumed a dark red colour. The bulk of the precipitate was then transferred to a flask and shaken up with 2 litres of distilled water. A clear, deep red, negatively charged sol was obtained.

Bimetallic Couples.—Five different couples were used, magnesium being one of the couple metals in each case. The other metals used for the bimetallic junctions were mono-, bi- and trivalent as follows :—Mg-Fe, Mg-Zn, Mg-Mn, Mg-Cu and Mg-Ag. They were prepared in the following manner, the experimental conditions being so fixed as to get reproducible activity for the couples as far as possible. Magnesium ribbon (10'' of 3 mm. width) was used in all cases. It was freshly cleaned with sand-paper, coiled up in the form of a spiral and then placed in the appropriate solution for 'coupling'. The solution taken for coupling was 25 c.c. in all cases. The strength of the solution as well as the time of coupling and washing are specified in Table I.

TABLE I

Couple.	Conc. of soln. for coupling.	Duration of coupling.	1st Wash- ing (under- tap).	2nd Wash- ing (50 c.c. dist.) water.	3rd Wash- ing (50 c.c. dist. water).	4th. Wash- ing (50 c.c. dist. water)
Mg-Fe	5% Soln. of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (prepared immediately before use)	1 min.	15 sec.	15 sec.	30 sec.	30 sec.
Mg-Zn	5% Soln. of $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$.	Do	"	"	"	"
Mg-Mn	5% Soln. of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Do	"	"	"	"
Mg-Cu	2.5% Soln. of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	10 sec.	20 sec.	"	"	"
Mg-Ag	0.5% Soln. of AgNO_3	15	15	"	"	"

The arrangement employed for the experiments consisted of a stout glass vessel of about 100 c.c. capacity, fitted with a rubber stopper and a glass tube through it. To the lower end of the glass tube was attached a small hook made of platinum wire to support the couple. The vessel was connected to a gas burette, and was illuminated by an electric lamp screened by a ground-glass plate. A wire was introduced between the screen and the vessel in the case of experiments with As_2S_3 sol.

To carry out an experiment, 50 c.c. of the sol were pipetted into the vessel. The couple, which was prepared as described above, was hung from the hook and the vessel closed tightly with the stopper. Then the vessel was gently tapped so that the couple fell into the sol. Observations of the progress of coagulation were made every minute. The experiments were conducted in a dark room and the bulb was switched on for a moment when an observation was made. In the case of As_2S_3 and Fe_2O_3 sols the vessel was allowed to stand undisturbed during coagulation but with V_2O_5 and Al_2O_3 sols it was shaken at intervals.

When the desired point of coagulation had been reached the volume of evolved gas was measured with the help of the gas burette. As the final point of coagulation the following were taken :—

Ferric oxide sol—when tiny specks of coagulum were just visible.

Vanadium pentoxide sol—when the sol was filled with streaks of coagulum, and had become very viscous and the couple within the bottle could not be easily seen.

Aluminium oxide sol—when the sol became so viscous that bubbles of evolved gas could not escape.

Arsenious sulphide sol—when the wire just disappeared from sight due to the increasing turbidity of the sol.

Employing any particular sol and a particular couple, three or four experiments were made and the mean value taken as the correct one. The results are shown in Table II.

To test the effect of junction potentials, suitable external potentials were applied to 50 c.c. of the various sols by means of platinum electrodes (about 2 sq. cm. each and fixed 0.5 cm. apart). The external potential was increased by steps of 0.5 volt till at a particular potential coagulation occurred in 6 hours or less. Thus the minimum coagulation voltage for each sol was determined. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE II

Couple.	As_2S_3 sol.		V_2O_5 sol.		Fe_3O_4 sol.		Al_2O_3 sol.	
	H_2 evolved.*	Coagul. time.	* H_2 evolved.	Coagul. time.	* H_2 evolved.	Coagul. time.	* H_2 evolved.	Coagul. time.
Mg-Fe	8.0 c.c.	42 min.	5.2 c.c.	46 min.	3.9 c.c.	20 min.	4.6	20 min.
Mg-Cu	2.1	24	4.9	52	2.1	13	3.5	18
Mg-Mn	2.4	45	6.1	18	6.1	10	3.4	11
Mg-Zn	3.9	20	5.6	69	1.5	9	2.7	15
Mg-Ag	1.2	57	2.8	74	6.4	51	5.0	10 hrs.

* At 760 mm. and at 23°.

TABLE III

Sol.	Minimum coagulation voltage.	
Fe_2O_3	Between 2.5 and 3.0 volts	
Al_2O_3	2.0	2.5
As_2S_3	3.0	3.5
V_2O_5	2.0	2.5

Of the colloids investigated coagulation by bimetallic junctions has been observed in each case. The rate of coagulation has been found to vary with the nature of the couple and the charge on the sol.

DISCUSSION

The two most obvious explanations which suggest themselves for coagulation of colloids by bimetallic junctions are (i) that the junction potential, however small, acts like an applied external potential and causes coagulation and (ii) that the electrolytes, formed by the action of the couple on water or on traces of acids that remain in the sol, cause coagulation in the usual way by lowering the charge on the colloid particles.

It has been pointed out by Biltz (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1908, 14, 567) that the junction potential is not the predominant cause of coagulation. From Table III it is apparent that the minimum coagulation voltage of each of the sols used is above 2.0 volts for a time interval of 6 hours. The junction potentials of the couples used in those experiments are not likely to exceed 1.0 volt in any case. Hence, it is clear that the effect of the junction potential is very insignificant, specially in view of the coagulation in most of the cases under investigation having occurred within an hour as against the interval of 6 hours employed to find the minimum coagulation voltage.

After complete coagulation of the sol, the clear supernatant liquid and the coagulum were separately tested for the respective metal ions (ions of the metals constituting the couple). Traces of the metal ions were invariably found present either in the clear supernatant liquid or in the coagulum or in both. Thus the electrolytes appear to play an important part in the coagulation phenomenon with couples, and so Schulze-Hardy law regarding the valency of coagulating ion is expected to hold in the case of the negatively charged sols. In the five couples taken for the present experiments, Mg is a common constituent. Any difference in the coagulation of the same sol with different couples might reasonably be attributed to the difference in the other metals. Of the other metals used, Ag is monovalent, Cu, Zn and Mn, divalent and Fe, trivalent. The couples containing Ag satisfy Schulze-Hardy law in as much as coagulation is most delayed with these couples. But the action of the bi- and trivalent metals appears to be anomalous from the above point of view. For example, Fe being trivalent, has in none of the two cases (As_2S_3 and V_2O_5 sols) been found to be the most effective coagulant. It is with the couples containing bivalent metals that coagulation has been found to occur most readily. The definite presence of metallic ions in the system, however, leads to the conclusion that electrolytic coagulation is one of the important factors during flocculation by couples.

During the experiments with the couples, nascent hydrogen is always evolved, and probably in the atomic state, and the atomic hydrogen is likely to be one of the factors involving coagulation. A significant point is that the hydrogen is evolved in the form of fine tiny bubbles. Thus copious new surface is generated and the adsorption effects on the newly generated surface might be factors in the process of coagulation. Stark (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2730) points out that

a pure Fe_2O_3 sol coagulates when a stream of an inert gas like hydrogen is passed through it. His experiments prove conclusively that coagulation is not due to impurities or free electrons associated with the gas. He postulates three possible mechanisms for the phenomenon. The effect might be due to increased collision of colloid particles consequent on agitation by gas bubbles; neutralisation of charge on the colloid by the charge on the gas bubble; adsorption effects on the gas-liquid interfaces produced by the gas bubbles. Stark himself has put forward abundant experimental evidence to show that "mechanical agitation is not the chief factor in the coagulation phenomenon with gas bubbles". Freundlich and Basu (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 115, 203) found that agitation accelerated the rate of coagulation of As_2S_3 , Fe_2O_3 and V_2O_5 sols by electrolytes. Retardation occurred with CuO and gold sols, which was attributed to peptisation. Freundlich and Kroch (*ibid.*, 1926, 124, 155) observed coagulation of CuO sol on vigorous stirring. Rate of coagulation was found to be proportional to the square of the rate of stirring. Freundlich and Loebmann (*ibid.*, 1928, 139, 368) observed similar results with graphite sol. Only a definite fraction of the colloidal particles could be coagulated by stirring. Freundlich and Reiklinghausen (*ibid.*, 1931, 157, 325) hold the view that stirring as such is not the cause of coagulation because a CuO sol does not coagulate if the stirring is such that the surface of the liquid is not disturbed or renewed. On the other hand, Heller (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 199, 354) maintains that particles can coagulate in the interior of a sol when they come into contact at high speeds. Heller (*ibid.*, 1934, 198, 1776) also claims that all sols can be mechanically coagulated under appropriate conditions as to pH etc. Thus, the role of agitation as a means of coagulation is still doubtful. If stirring is really a cause in the coagulation phenomenon, its speed must be a very important factor. A fairly vigorous stirring is essential for any appreciable amount of coagulation to occur. In the present experiments 1.2 to 6.4 c. c. of the gas have been evolved in 10 to 74 minutes. The rate of evolution of the gas is thus not very vigorous and it may be taken that mechanical agitation does not play any appreciable role.

It has been pointed out by several authors (Lenard, *Ann. Physik*, 1892, 46, 584; Thomson, McLean and Galt, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1895, 57, A. 335; Coehn and Mozer, *Ann. Physik*, 1914, iv, 43, 1048) that bubbles of inert gases suspended in water are negatively charged. McTaggart (*Phil. Mag.*, 1913, vi, 27, 297; 1914, 28, 367; 1922, 44, 386) measured the charge on gas bubbles while immersed in a liquid by observing the rate of cataphoresis of small bubbles in water and solutions of electrolytes and non-electrolytes. He has also shown "that the magnitude and even the sign of this charge might be changed by the addition of small quantities of electrolytes". It is thus possible that coagulation of a sol might occur by neutralisation of the charge on the particle by the charge on the gas bubbles. If the charge on the bubble is opposite to that on the colloid particle, it is to be expected that the larger the volume of hydrogen evolved, the more rapid should be the coagulation. In the present experiments the volumes of hydrogen evolved have been plotted against the time of coagulation (curve not shown). With negatively charged sols the

time of coagulation with different couples increases as the amount of evolved hydrogen decreases. A somewhat opposite effect is observed with the positively charged sols. The nature of the curves obtained in the present experiments in the cases of negatively charged As_2S_3 and V_2O_5 sols is thus explicable. But in the absence of sufficient data we cannot be sure if this is actually the case.

If, on the other hand, the charge on the gas bubbles is of the same sign as that on the colloid particles, we might very well suppose that instead of coagulation, a stabilisation of the sol will occur. This might be the reason for the effect observed with positively charged sols in the present experiments. Even if the above effects do operate, they are only partial in view of other factors at work tending to coagulate the sol; for example, the electrolyte, formed by the action of the couple on the dispersion medium, has definitely a coagulating effect. Thus, in spite of the stabilising influence of the gas, the sol might ultimately coagulate, but the time of coagulation is prolonged.

Freundlich and Loebmann (*loc. cit.*) ascribed mechanical coagulation of goethite sol (by a current of air) to an enlargement of the surface of contact. Deutsch (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 136, 353) observed a colour change in certain indicators when their aqueous solutions were shaken with air. He is of opinion that the increased aggregation of particles in the surface layer is due to the greater surface activity of larger particles. Freundlich and Recklinghausen (*loc. cit.*) have shown that for mechanical coagulation of colloids it is necessary that the surface be constantly changed. Thus it is established that the sol-air interface is an important factor in the coagulation phenomenon. Orientation of particles in the surface layer may be a secondary effect as has been pointed out by Freundlich and Loebmann (*Koll.-Chem Beih.*, 1929, 28, 391). McTaggart has shown "that bubbles of inert gases suspended in solutions of electrolytes absorb on their surfaces the ions present in solution. In like manner colloids are adsorbed from dilute sols". The phenomenon of coagulation of colloids by hydrogen bubbles might then be pictured as follows. The bubble while rising through the sol absorbs particles of colloid. When these bubbles finally reach the surface of the liquid and burst, the excess is delivered to a very thin layer of the liquid at the top. The excess goes on increasing as more and more bubbles burst till finally the concentration limit at which the sol is stable is exceeded and the sol coagulates. It is likely that the evolved hydrogen functions in a similar manner in the present experiments also.

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